

Evaluation of data in the Iron-Age- Danube database (<https://iron-age-danube.eu>)

**Supporting document for the development of the Iron Age
landscapes strategies in the Danube region (Output 3.2)**

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Table of contents

Introduction.....	3
General information on cultural heritage in participating countries.....	3
Austria	4
Croatia	5
Hungary	6
Slovenia	7
Structure of the Iron-Age-Danube Database	8
Data sources and input methodology in participating countries.....	9
Austria	10
Croatia	11
Hungary	12
Slovenia	14
National evaluation and international comparison of the entered data.....	15
Topic Archaeological research.....	17
Topic Protection of archaeological heritage	19
Topic Promotion of archaeological heritage and its integration in tourism	23
Recommendations for transnational strategies based on the data evaluation.....	26
Conclusion and outlook.....	28
Literature.....	28
Appendix 1 – Research methods terminology used in the Iron-Age-Danube database.....	29
Appendix 2 – Decision options on the topic of monument protection used in the Iron-Age-Danube database.....	33
Appendix 3 – Decision options on the topic of promotion and tourism used in the Iron-Age-Danube database.....	34

Introduction

Over the past few decades, European archaeological heritage gained major attention by connecting prominent archaeological sites to wider transnational networks, which have become a popular tool for their protection, promotion and tourist use. Imposingly attractive, however very fragile, prehistoric landscapes in the Danube program area remain partly hidden and not well integrated into cultural tourism. The Iron-Age-Danube project focuses on monumental archaeological landscapes of the Early Iron Age, characterized by, e.g., fortified hilltop settlements and large tumulus cemeteries, from the era between roughly the 9th–4th cent. BC (Hallstatt period). At that time, the Danube region was part of a cultural phenomenon called the Eastern-Hallstatt circle.

The Iron-Age-Danube project is part of the EU-program Interreg Danube Transnational Programme/ DTP and is funded by European Regional Development Fund. Duration of the project is between 1st January 2017 and 30th of September 2019. Between April 2017 and October 2018 eleven project partners and nine associated partners from five countries (Austria, Croatia, Hungary, Slovakia and Slovenia) conducted researches with modern technologies on the archaeological heritage of the Early Iron Age (Hallstatt period) in the frame of four international Archaeological Camps (Camp Austria 2017, Camp Croatia 2017, Camp Slovenia 2018 and Camp Hungary 2018).

Furthermore, the project partners will establish common international strategies for research, protection and sustainable touristic use of archaeological heritage in the whole Danube area. As tool for the implementation of the strategies a database was created in collaboration with the Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities (ACDH) / Austrian Academy of Sciences, that helps to evaluate and understand the Iron Age heritage in the term of research activities, status of monument protection and potential for touristic use. The collected data are accessible to researchers and general public (<https://iron-age-danube.eu/>).

General information on cultural heritage in participating countries

In the frame of the Iron-Age-Danube project the publication “Researching archaeological landscapes across borders. Strategies, Methods and Decisions for the 21st Century”, edited by Zoltán Czajlik, Matija Črešnar, Michael Doneus, Martin Fera, Anja Hellmuth Kramberger and Marko Mele, comprehensively compared legislative for the protection of the archaeological heritage in participating countries¹. Therefore, in this evaluation the legal framework is not

¹ Pages 43-78.

presented again. In the following, some statistical information on cultural heritage in the participating countries is available.

Austria

The term "monument" covers a wide spectrum, from the Stone Age burial to the housing of the classical modern age, from the Roman camp to the baroque pin, from the chapel to the historical industrial building and from the local ensemble to the figure of a saint. The Federal Monuments Office has to list immovable monuments, which are under monument protection, in a list and make this list publicly known. As a rule, this is done by an entry on the website of the Federal Monuments Office: List of monuments. The fact that a protected monument is present is indicated also in the landowner register.

39.367 objects are listed as under protection . They are distributed as follows:

Burgenland	2.086 objects,
Kärnten	2.856 objects
Niederösterreich	10.588 objects
Oberösterreich	5.897 objects
Salzburg	2.196 objects
Steiermark	4.940 objects
Tirol	4.841 objects
Vorarlberg	1.624 objects
Wien	3.339 objects

Of these monuments, 125 are units (legally called "Ensembles"). Also, 56 Parks and gardens are listed in an Attachment to the Federal Act on the Protection of Monuments Due to Their Historic, Artistic or Other Cultural Significance (Monument Protection Act – MPA) under "Constitutional Provision Table of the Parks and Gardens pursuant to § 1 para. 12"

As for archaeological monuments, there are currently 1029 individually protected, 128 of these via listing (stand June 2019).

The Database of the Department of Archaeology includes 23.350 catalogued sites (stand June 2019).

Croatia

According to the latest data from September 2017, 9.417 Cultural goods were entered in the Register of Cultural Goods of the Republic of Croatia, registered on three lists: the List of Protected Cultural Goods, the List of Cultural Goods of National Significance and the List of Preventively Protected Goods.

Number and categories of cultural goods in Croatia

- 6838 immovable cultural goods
- 6229 individually protected immovable cultural goods
- 596 cultural and historical units
- 2415 mobile cultural goods
- 164 non-material cultural goods
- 13 cultural landscapes

Number and subtype of cultural goods

Individually protected immovable goods

- 1031 archaeological sites (869 land archaeological sites and 162 underwater archaeological sites)
- 2067 sacral buildings and complexes
- 2189 buildings and complexes (1110 public buildings, 854 residential buildings and 225 residential and commercial buildings)
- 594 memorial buildings and complexes
- 189 military buildings and complexes
- 13 urban equipment
- 146 other types of immovable cultural goods

Cultural-historical ensembles

- 111 archaeological zones (93 archaeological zones and 18 underwater archaeological zones)
- cultural and historical monuments of the urban character (202), cultural and historical ensembles of the rural character (173), cultural and historical ensembles of the industrial character (17)
- 392 cultural and historical units and parts of cultural-
- 65 historical-memorial units
- 29 other types of cultural and historical monuments

Movable cultural goods

- 1273 individually protected movable cultural goods
- 961 collections
- 181 museum artefacts (within which 1021 museum collections are protected).

Hungary

There are two basic levels of protection for monuments and archaeological sites:

- Registered sites and monuments are generally protected by law,
- A higher level of protection is provided by an act (ministerial decree) for archaeological sites or monuments declared to be protected. Protected sites can either benefit from enhanced protection (in case of a site with scientific significance, and high importance for a larger region) or a high level of protection (in case of a site with exceptional scientific significance and international or national importance).

There are sites that are under archaeological and monumental protection as well. An archaeological protection zone can be designated around the protected sites, the task of which is to ensure the sustainability, accessibility and landscape protection of the protected site.

Following data are available in the central official National Site Register maintained by the responsible deputy state secretariat of the Prime Minister's Office (access April 2019):

Number and categories of protected archaeological sites in Hungary

- 60398 identified archaeological sites in the register
- 60210 topographically identified sites

- 1952 archaeological sites under unique protection
- 256 archaeological sites under enhanced protection
- 1696 highly protected archaeological sites
- 111 archaeological protection zones

Number and categories of protected monuments in Hungary

- 3111 objects under general monument protection
- 11667 monuments and ensembles under unique monument protection
- 918 designated monument environments
- 47 sites of historical interest
- 1 historic landscape

Slovenia

Slovenian cultural heritage is divided into 3 main categories – moveable cultural heritage, immovable cultural heritage and intangible cultural heritage. The institution responsible for the making and management of lists and registers of cultural heritage is the Ministry for Culture of the Republic of Slovenia . Currently, registers of intangible and immovable heritage are up and running, but there is still no unified register of movable cultural heritage. The vast majority of movable cultural heritage is located in public museums, which manage their own inventory databases. The remainder of the movable heritage is located in private museums and collections whose inventory is not so well-documented.

The list of intangible cultural heritage is currently (March 2019) comprised of 69 entries.

The Register of immovable cultural heritage, where all scientifically recognized immovable heritage entities, both underwater and terrestrial, are listed and spatially defined, is much vaster. As of march 2019, it included 30095 entries, dispersed into 10 types of heritage:

- archaeological heritage (3561 entries),
- buildings (16050),
- parks and gardens (218),
- buildings with parks and gardens (120),
- memorial buildings and places (7852),

- other buildings and devices (807),
- settlements and its parts (1160),
- cultural landscape (317),
- other (9),
- unknown (1)

Most of the registered immovable cultural heritage sites are also protected.

Structure of the Iron-Age-Danube Database

The database represents a relational data-collection, which gives internal and external users the opportunity, to insert and extract multiple information about archaeological heritage from the participating countries, namely Austria, Croatia, Hungary and Slovenia. The structure of the database consists from four major datasets, namely SITE, ARCHAEOLOGICAL ENTITY, RESEARCH ACTIVITY and MONUMENT PROTECTION. Additionally, the dataset SITE provides information about possibilities for touristic use in the set TOURISM. Major feature of the datasets SITE, ARCHAEOLOGICAL ENTITIES, RESEARCH ACTIVITY and MONUMENT PROTECTION are spatial polygons in an interactive map. Generic (square) polygons indicate archaeological sites or archaeological entities which cannot be defined in their exact spatial extend or for which it is not possible to give detailed information about the spatial extent of research activities or areas that fall under monument protection. The dataset SITE is the highest class in the database and includes on the one hand geographical and administrative information about the area where the past human activity has been recognized as well as a short description of the site, related literature and, as mentioned above, information about possibilities for touristic use on the other hand. Linked to the dataset SITE can be research activities (RESEARCH ACTIVITY), archaeological entities (related ARCH ENTITIES) or “monument protection” entries (related MONUMENT PROTECTION). The data set RESEARCH ACTIVITY comprises data on archaeological research conducted on a specific site. Information about the period of time during which the research took place, the responsible researcher and the research methods are provided inter alia. The data set ARCH ENTITIES comprises data on all entities such as cemetery or settlement. The archaeological entity itself is defined by a specific human activity (entity type), period of this activity (dating) and spatial location (polygon inside of the site). In deciding whether two or more archaeological entities should

be merged to one site in the IAD database, the dating of the entities, spatial proximity, the topography of the region and archaeological experience were taken into account.

As it also counts for RESEARCH ACTIVITY, there can be several archaeological entities related to single site. Information on type, topography, dating and certainty can be found within the data set ARCH ENTITIES. The data set MONUMENT PROTECTION gives basic information about threats, current land use and the cultural heritage status. The data set TOURISM, which can be accessed from the dataset SITE, comprises information about accessibility, visibility and long-term management of the archaeological heritage as well as information about given infrastructure and potential of the surroundings for touristic use. The methodology for the tourism evaluation is oriented on the publication “Archäologische Biographie einer Landschaft an der steirisch-slowenischen Grenze / Arheološka biografija krajine ob meji med avstrijsko Štajersko in Slovenijo” by Matija Črešnar, Marko Mele, Karl Peitler and Manca Vinazza (<http://www.interarch-steiermark.eu/publikationen.html>).

Data extraction retrieval is possible for each dataset separately by using several search functions. However, the SITE section includes also search options of other datasets, namely:

- Advanced search options
- Location search options
- Research Activity search options
- Arch. Entity search options
- Periods
- Monument protection search options

Outputs of the database are (exportable) lists and tables with search results, interactive maps and spatial data, as well as visualizations of statistic results.

Data sources and input methodology in participating countries

The data was collected by reviewing and extracting the required information from multiple sources. In the majority published and publicly available data was used. The literature sources (bibliography) used for data collection were entered in the Zotero bibliographic database, which was synchronized with the IAD database. Spatial data from published papers (maps, cadastral parcels numbers, GPS points, and site location descriptions) were verified in other Geoportals and managed in a GIS-software (QGIS).

The time of research and scale of the research differs considerably. Many research activities that were conducted in the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th century have poor or even non-existing documentation, so the exact spatial definition of the research area

cannot be made. If the general area of the research can be reconstructed, a square indicating the wider area was made and if the location cannot be determined at all, there is no polygon for the research activity. For the research that was carried out after WW2 the exact location is known in most cases, because the areas of the published research are referenced to the cadastral system.

Austria

For Austria were defined three different levels of data on Iron Age heritage. Level 1 are the micro-regions Großklein and Strettweg with the highest level of data density. The second level is the federal state of Styria in which the micro-regions are located, with a little less sources and data density. Level 3 is whole Austria, which has been entered by analyzing only most important sources and therefore the data density is lower. Different approaches have been intentionally selected in order to show the impact of intensive research on the knowledge density. This knowledge on archaeological heritage is namely the basis for any further strategic decisions in monument protection or tourism.

As the highest level, the two Austrian micro-regions Großklein and Strettweg were considered. For the micro-regions, every available source of information was used. The determination of sites was carried out by means of searches in archives, local files (Ortsakten), publications, new evaluation of ALS scans and ortho-photos provided by GIS-Styria, fieldwalking surveys, geophysical prospections, small trial excavations and long-term research excavations. Different analog and digital data collections, created in previous projects, could also be used. Basic data was provided by Susanne Tiefengraber, which worked on the topic in the past decade in the framework of the project „SCHULATLAS STEIERMARK“² as well as during the ALS-scan and aerial photo analyses for the Federal Monuments Office. In addition, the data collections carried out in the frame of the EU-projects InterArch-Steiermark and BorderArch-Steiermark³ were used. Extensive research, respectively evaluation of ALS-scans and ortho-photos provided by GIS-Styria, were performed by Sarah Kizster and Stephanie Gaberz in the frame of the project BorderArch-Steiermark as well as by Patricia Raggam in the frame of the Iron-Age-Danube project. For the micro-region Strettweg also available information on single finds was taken into account. In this way, a significant amount of information on archaeological sites could be gathered for the two micro-regions.

It must be noted, that the records determined thereby had to be repeatedly evaluated and adjusted. In particular, analysis of ALS data has revealed a large amount of terrain features that are potential archaeological legacies. Particularly evident in this context are the burial

² <https://www.schulatlas.at/>

³ <http://www.interarch-steiermark.eu/>

mounds. However, terrain features determined in this way can not be dated per se, making their inclusion in a survey on "Iron Age sites" problematic. For example, while burial mounds, which may be either Iron Age or from the Roman period, have been discussed in the Iron Age Danube landscape study, very uncertain sites have not been included in the database.

The second highest level was the federal state of Styria, since within Styria the two micro-regions are located. The data collection for Styria included the same main sources as for the micro-regions Großklein and Strettweg, with the exception that the analysis of ALS-scans and ortho-photos provided by GIS-Styria was not conducted as extensively for the entire federal state. Furthermore, the latest unpublished research results were not considered.

All other Austrian federal states (Vienna, Lower Austria, Upper Austria, Tyrol, Salzburg, Vorarlberg and Burgenland)⁴ with exception of Carinthia⁵, were considered as basic level. Basis of the data collection are the "Fundberichte aus Österreich", the archeological publication series of the Federal Monuments Agency (Bundesdenkmalamt)⁶. The series is published annually and presents information on all archaeological activities carried out over the course of a year. Beyond that, some information on sites published in scientific monographs was also partially included.

Croatia

In the database data about the sites of the Continental Croatia in the area enclosed by the Rivers Danube, Sava, Drava, Mura, and Kupa was entered. Reasons for limiting the reference area arise from the previously defined scope of the "Iron-Age Danube" project, which deals exclusively with the Early Iron Age landscapes associated with the Eastern Hallstatt Cultural Circle, and which do not exist in the area south of the River Kupa. Also, Croatian regions of Istria, Kvarner, Gorski Kotar, Lika, Dalmatia, Dalmatian hinterland and the islands have a completely different cultural dynamics during the Iron Age which is not comparable to the Continental Croatia. Another reason for not including the mentioned area is the lack of chronologically relevant material for comparison and a lack of sites researched on the adequate level (especially settlements).

The IAD Database collected data about archaeological sites in the Continental Croatia, covering 14 counties. These are Požega-Slavonia, Varaždin, Koprivnica-Krževci, City of Zagreb, Zagreb, Krapina-Zagorje, Međimurje, Bjelovar-Bilogora, Virovitica-Podravina, Brod-Posavina, Osijek-Baranja, Vukovar-Srijem, Karlovac and Sisak-Moslavina Counties.

⁴ One of the basic sources for the mapping of Iron Age sites in Austria were maps prepared by Denkmalamt Österreich (E. Steigberger).

⁵ For Carinthia Martin Fera provided more extensive data as taken on account for other federal states.

⁶ <https://bda.gv.at/de/publikationen/fundberichte-aus-oesterreich/>

Data for the IAD database was collected⁷ from publications containing information about archaeological research, as well as scientific and professional papers from scientific journals (printed or published on the Internet).⁸

Since there was no predetermined universal format for publishing reports of archaeological research in the Republic of Croatia, up to 2004 when Croatian Archaeological Yearbook started to be published annually, the quality of data entered is inevitably linked to the quality of the existing publications.

Likewise, the quality of data from published data sources systematically excavated sites is more complete and coherent, than from trial research excavations and reconnaissance surveys.

The same dichotomy in data quality is noticeable when reviewing older and newer publications. Furthermore, due to the lack of systematically and scientifically processed and published research results and the general poor state of research in the area at hand especially pertaining to certain sites (rescue and trial researched sites, surveyed sites), precise chronological determination can be difficult. Only a general attribution of sites to the Early Iron Age was in some cases possible.

In addition, in the above-mentioned cases, and for the above-mentioned reasons, there is a lack of accurate spatial data, which would allow for a comparison between the coverage of the entire site and its researched parts (and in particular, the parts researched by different methods). Furthermore, the same applies to the data about the exact protected areas of the sites. The Cultural Heritage Registry of the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Croatia available on-line only publishes descriptive positions of the protected archaeological sites.

Hungary

⁷ Data for IAD-database was collected by Marta Rakvin and Anja Bertol Stipetić (Archaeological Museum Zagreb) and Martina Jurišić (Institute of Archaeology), while Marta Rakvin was responsible for data entry.

⁸ 1. Hrvatski arheološki godišnjak / Croatian Archaeological Yearbook (Croatian Ministry of Culture 2004-2014); 2. Registar arheoloških nalaza i nalazišta sjeverozapadne Hrvatske / Registry of Archaeological Finds and Sites of North-western Croatia, Museum society of NW Croatia, Bjelovar 1990 & 1997; 3. Izdanja Hrvatskog arheološkog društva, Croatian Archaeological Society, Zagreb; 4. Obavijesti Hrvatskog arheološkog društva, Croatian Archaeological Society, Zagreb; 5. Prilozi Arheološkog Instituta u Zagrebu, Institute of Archaeology, Zagreb; 6. Annales Instituti Archaeologici, Institute of Archaeology, Zagreb; 7. Vjesnik Arheološkog muzeja u Zagrebu, Archaeological museum in Zagreb, Zagreb; 8. Opuscula Archaeologica, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, University of Zagreb; 9. Arheološki radovi i rasprave, Croatian Academy of Sciences and Arts, Zagreb; 10. Muzejski vjesnik, Varaždin; 11. Osječki zbornik, Osijek; 12. Podravski zbornik, Koprivnica; 13. Glasnik slavonskih muzeja, Osijek; 14. Histria Antiqua, Pula; 15. Zbornik Mosalvine, Kutina; 16. Arheološki pregled, Beograd; 17. Registry of cultural goods of the Republic of Croatia (<https://www.minkulture.hr/default.aspx?id=6212>); 18. Archive of the Archaeological Museum in Zagreb

In the database the data about the Hallstatt sites of the Hungarian region Transdanubia in the area enclosed by current country borders and the River Danube was entered. The cultural limitation is due to the previously defined scope of the “Iron-Age Danube” project, which deals exclusively with the Early Iron Age landscapes associated with the Eastern Hallstatt Cultural Circle, therefore sites of the Mezőcsát-, the Scythian Vekerzug and the early La Tène culture were excluded, which also sets the timeframe of the entered data.

The IAD Database collected data about archaeological sites in Transdanubia, covering Győr-Moson-Sopron, Komárom-Esztergom, Vas, Veszprém, Fejér, Zala, Somogy, Tolna, Baranya counties, as well as the area of Pest county and the city of Budapest west of the Danube.

Data for the IAD database was collected from the following sources⁹:

- The primary source was the central official National Site Register created by the National Office of Cultural Heritage and maintained by the Prime Minister’s Office, which contains every archaeological sites ever reported to the authorities, regardless of the method of the discovery (visible archaeological heritage, field walking survey, excavation, aerial archaeology, geophysical methods etc.), including the type, dating, conducted activities reported about these sites. These entries also have a polygon attached to them, which were also provided for the IAD database.
- We also reached out to some of the local archaeologists for help in the dating of unpublished material existing in or outside of the above-mentioned database from Vas and Veszprém (Gábor Ilon), Győr-Moson-Sopron (Attila Mrenka, Ferenc Újvári), Zala (Bálint Havasi, Csilla Száraz) counties and Budapest (Gábor Szilas, Márton Farkas Tóth).
- Publications containing information about archaeological research, as well as scientific and professional papers from scientific journals (printed or published on the Internet).¹⁰

⁹ Data for IAD Database was collected by András Jáky, Bence Soós (Eötvös Loránd University) and Gergő István Farkas (Prime Minister’s Office, Department for Cultural Heritage Protection and Development), while András Jáky was responsible for data entry.

¹⁰ 1. Acta Archaeologica Academiae Scientiarum Hungaricae, Hungarian Academy of Sciences, Research Centre for the Humanities. Institute of Archaeology, Budapest; 2. Antaeus, Hungarian Academy of Sciences, Research Centre for the Humanities. Institute of Archaeology, Budapest; 3. Aquincumi Füzetek, Budapest History Museum, Aquincum Museum, Budapest; 4. Archaeologiai Értesítő, Hungarian Society for Archaeology and Art History Budapest; 5. Arrabona, Rómer Flóris Art and Historic Museum, Győr; 6. Communicationes Archaeologicae Hungariae, Hungarian National Museum, Budapest; 7. Dissertationes Archaeologicae ex Instituto Archaeologico Universitatis de Rolando Eötvös nominatae, Eötvös Loránd University, Budapest; 8. Folia Archaeologia, Hungarian National Museum, Budapest; 9. Régészeti Füzetek, Hungarian National Museum, Budapest; 10. Régészeti Kutatások Magyarországon / Archaeological Investigations in Hungary, National Office of Cultural Heritage - Hungarian National Museum, Budapest; 11. Savaria - A Vas Megyei Múzeumok értesítője, Szombathely; 12. Somogyi Múzeumok Közleményei, Kaposvár; 13. Tatabányai Múzeum Évkönyve, Tatabánya; 14. Veszprém Megyei Múzeumi Közlemények, Veszprém; 15. Wosinsky Mór Múzeum Évkönyve, Szekszárd; 16. Zalai Múzeum, Zalaegerszeg; 17. other available publications and domestic and foreign scientific and professional literature such as papers, monographies and conference volumes.

For data collection only reliable data was used, with evidence for the dating and cultural affiliation meaning published and publicly available data, and the data that were confirmed by local archaeologists. This main principle was set based on Zoltán Czajlik's long experience of archaeological site data collecting in Hungary, due to 25 years of aerial archaeological research and many different projects. The reason for these limitations has roots in the Hungarian research of the Hallstatt culture. Unfortunately, in the Hungarian archaeological research the study of the Hallstatt culture was not as represented as other prehistoric cultures in both education and the focus of archaeologists on the field. This affects the reliability of the discovered and reported Hallstatt sites. For example, non-visible sites are usually discovered by field walking surveys, and most of the time, it is difficult to differentiate between Late Bronze Age and Early Iron Age sites based on the sherds found on the surface. Knowing this, the Hungarian partners decided on leaving out "Hallstatt" sites with unseen/unprocessed material to provide reliable data for the database. This decision was proven right, when local archaeologist helped us with more up-to-date data, and for example in the case of Budapest, more than half of the registered "Early Iron Age sites" were proven to be dated incorrectly, as they mainly belonged to the Urnfield period. Single finds without information on the type of the site they belong to were also left out from the data entry.

The Hungarian site concept stand closer to the archaeological entities than the sites in the logic of the IAD database. If one entity also defined the whole site, the same polygon was applied for the archaeological entity and the site entry. If one Hungarian site covered more than one types of entity, the same polygon was applied for these different entities. Most of the polygons entered into the database for these archaeological entities was provided by responsible Department of the Prime Minister's Office, however, in some cases, they needed correction based on the literature. Polygons for sites that are not included in the National Site Register, and for research activities (such as the extension of excavation trenches) were also created on the basis of the literature, if that information was available.

It has to be highlighted, that the quality of the data is mainly correlates with the quality of the existing publications, as the National Site Register only contains basic information on the research activities, and the extensions of the sites are defined by features from all archaeological periods, not only the area of the Early Iron Age features.

Slovenia

For the purpose of the IAD database, data about all relevant early Iron Age sites in Slovenia was collected. Even though the so called Štajerska, Koroška and Dolenjska Hallstatt groups are a part of the eastern Hallstatt circle and the groups in central and western Slovenia are more

inclined to the contemporary cultures in Italy and the Adriatic, data for sites in whole Slovenia were collected.

Data collection for the IAD database was carried out using all the relevant published and publicly available articles and literature as well as some relevant web-based registers about archaeological heritage and Iron Age sites in Slovenia .

Spatial data about the entered sites, entities and monument protection and research polygons was made and/or verified using GIS. The verification compared the current areas of protection for the sites in the Register of immovable cultural heritage of Slovenia, the cadastral maps, ALS and satellite imagery with the proposed polygons of the sites entered into the IAD database.

Most of the known archaeological sites in Slovenia are protected so almost all the entities, defined in the IAD database have a monument protection polygon issued by the government. The monument protection polygon does not always overlap completely with the whole entity.

National evaluation and international comparison of the entered data

In this chapter a basic statistical analysis of the data in the Iron-Age-Danube database is presented. The comparison of data, which was entered using same standards, enables us to compare results from different countries, in order to discern issues, which are common to all countries and need to be included in joint transnational strategies. The analysis is tackling three topics: archaeological research, protection of archaeological heritage and promotion of archaeological heritage and its integration of tourism. We are fully aware that the entered data might be incomplete and that some evaluations during the entering of the data can be very subjective. But still, the analysis of the data should at least show some problems and trends, which can be tackled by joint transnational strategies.

In the database overall 1046 Iron Age sites with multiple entities were entered, of which 3 sites are extended over two countries. Most sites were entered for Austria, then Slovenia, Croatia (continental Croatia) and Hungary (Transdanubia) (*fig. 1*). The different amount of sites depends strongly on the history of research, the availability of the data and the geography in each country. The areas considered for collecting the data were 31.889 km² in Croatia (only continental Croatia), 83.879 km² in Austria, 20.273 km² in Slovenia and 38.000 km² in Hungary (only Transdanubia). The highest density of entered sites has Slovenia with more than 8 sites per 1000 km², followed by Austria with round 7,5 sites and Croatia with almost 5 sites. The lowest density is in Transdanubia with round 2,5 sites per 1000 km² (*fig. 1*). Since there are differences in the intensity of the data availability and acquisition also inside one countries (e.g. three different levels in Austria) this evaluation is merely indicative.

Fig. 1: Quantity of sites dated in the Early Iron Age in participating countries.

Since the ownership of the land with archaeological monuments, has an indirect impact on research, monument protection and tourism, we will consider this data first. The information on land-owners is not always easy to get, so we have some gaps in the data sets (4 – information not available). Still we can see some trends in different countries. During the data acquisition we were trying to find out if the site is in 1 – private, 2 – public or 3 – private and public ownership. In all four countries the sites are mostly in 1 – private or 3 – private and public ownership (*fig. 2*). This isn't really a surprise, since the sites in the focus of our project, like hilltop settlements and tumulus cemeteries, mostly cover larger areas. The most representative data we have for Croatia, where we can clearly see the diversity of land ownership types. The private land ownership brings sometimes more difficulties to implement monument protection actions and to ensure the long term management of the heritage. In Austria it means also additional negotiations on the ownership of movable archaeological finds. Also the accessibility for archaeological research can be limited due to decisions by private owners. However, the private ownership also brings some positive initiatives, if added value for the economical development built on archaeological heritage can be recognized by the owners.

Fig. 2: ownership of the land with archaeological sites dated in the Early Iron Age.

Topic Archaeological research

In the last years the archaeological research adopted a series of different methods, which can be implemented on Iron Age sites. The use of the methods has some advantages and limitations, which were presented in the projects publication “Researching archaeological landscapes across borders. Strategies, Methods and Decisions for the 21st Century”, edited by Zoltán Czajlik, Matija Črešnar, Michael Doneus, Martin Fera, Anja Hellmuth Kramberger and Marko Mele. In our database the partners could select over 100 methods or their variations, which can be basically divided between invasive and non-invasive methods (*fig. 3*). A comparison shows that invasive methods (excavation) are still prevailing in all four countries, which has a lot to do also with the history of research. Archaeological excavations were and partly are still considered to be the major method for archaeological research. Due to the development of new prospection methods the non-invasive methods, like aerial photography or ALS, uncovered a big amount of new sites and are applied more frequently, also in combination with other methods.

Fig. 3: invasive and non-invasive methods used on archaeological sites dated in the Early Iron Age.

Besides excavations many sites have been researched/identified by field walking (*fig. 4*). Geophysics, remote sensing, geomorphological research, surface geometry survey and environmental survey, all different prospection methods, are represented beyond 10%, but are all together a strong tool for

research of Iron Age sites. Desktop assessment and artefact studies are part of any serious research project and are therefore also strongly represented.

Fig. 4: most important groups of methods used on archaeological sites dated in the Early Iron Age.

In the following we would like to compare the engagement of selected methods in participating countries, which are considered by the project partnership as most relevant for the research of archaeological landscapes.

Remote sensing techniques are combining three major groups of methods: satellite imaging, airborne sensing and low altitude survey (e.g. drone photography). Generally remote sensing is not very well represented in the database, since only 56 from 1046 sites have been researched by the mentioned methods. Hungary, Austria and Slovenia seem to be further in the application of these methods on such sites as Croatia (*fig. 5*).

Fig. 5: archaeological sites dated to the Early Iron Age researched by remote sensing techniques and ALS.

One of the important remote sensing techniques, which have been implemented in the last decade is the ALS (Airborne Laser Scanning). A comparison shows that Austria and Slovenia are making good progress with that method (*fig. 5*), partly also because of good coverage and accessible ALS data for those two countries.

Another method on the up-rise is geophysics. The constant development of technology and the possibility to cover larger areas makes it attractive for archaeological research. Overall, we are dealing with 83 sites from 1046, which have included geophysics in the research. Austria, Slovenia and Hungary are implementing this method more intensively on Iron Age sites as Croatia (*fig. 6*)

Fig. 6: archaeological sites dated to the Early Iron Age researched by geophysics and field walking.

Another successful method for covering larger areas is field walking. This well established archaeological research method is very well represented also on Iron Age sites, where almost half of all sites (439) were also researched by this method. The implementation of the method, which has no major technical requirements, seems to be a bit more intensive in Hungary, Austria and Croatia than in Slovenia (*fig. 6*).

Topic Protection of archaeological heritage

The Iron-Age-Danube database includes few themes connected to the topic of monument protection. In our data input we included long term management evaluation, cultural and natural heritage status, different threats, often connected also with the land use etc. This data enables us to create an international comparison of the major heritage issues for the Iron Age heritage of the Danube region.

The analysis of our long-term management possibilities is based on three basic categories: 1 – long-term care is ensured, 2 – short-term care is ensured and 3 – no care foreseen or possible. The long-term management in the project needs to be understood from the standpoint of existence of any plans or initiatives (mostly local), which take care of the site from the perspective of monument protection or tourism use. The basic comparison of the data (*fig. 7*) shows that in all countries most of the sites are, besides the basic execution of monument protection laws and general strategies on national monument protection, actually not managed at all. It is interesting that in Austria and Slovenia the short-term care is relatively well represented and exceeds even the long-term care, what is not the case in Croatia and Hungary. In Austria and Slovenia in general the amount of Iron Age sites with some care ensured is over 20%, but in Croatia and Hungary we are staying at up to 10%.

Fig. 7: Management of archaeological sites dated in the Early Iron Age.

Another important comparison in the protection of archaeological heritage topic is on cultural heritage status (*fig. 8*). Since we are dealing with different monument protection systems in the analyzed countries as described above, generally any kind of heritage status was researched during the data entry. Many archaeological sites from the Iron Age are widely dispersed in the landscape, so it is understandable that the process of gaining heritage status is in most cases not yet finished and depends on procedure complexity in different countries. Exception among the countries is Slovenia, with an efficient heritage registration system, which allows for the sites to get a protection status very quickly¹¹. But still, there are many sites, which have a bigger extent than originally predicted and protected and are therefore marked as “partly” protected. This seems to be the case in all countries, especially since the new research methods and technologies enabled the researchers to provide extensive amount of new data on this sites, which have not yet been fully included in the monument protection. Monument protection procedures and the integration of new research data in the monument protection seem to be also reflected by many sites, which have no official heritage status.

¹¹ In Hungary there are two levels of protection: 1.) the general protections (ex lege protection or protection by the force of law), which considers all sites which are entered to the National Site Register and 2.) the enhanced or high-level protection status. So each registered Hungarian Iron Age site can be considered to have a cultural heritage status, which means that in case of any development on these sites the heritage authority prescribes the necessary archaeological intervention. In the evaluation the difference between the two levels of protection was considered.

Fig. 8: Cultural heritage status of archaeological sites dated in the Early Iron Age.

For the protection of Iron Age monuments also the natural heritage status of the sites is important (fig. 9). Not only because it reduces the building activity, which could destroy archaeological heritage, but also because it can provide monitoring by additionally trained natural protection officers. In our research area the Iron Age heritage in Hungary and Slovenia seem to have advantages of the natural heritage protection with up to 11% of all registered sites. In Croatia and Austria this combination of natural and cultural heritage does not seem to have an important impact.

Fig. 9: Early Iron Age sites located in the natural protection areas.

The archaeological heritage can be threatened by many different activities at the same time. In our analysis we tried to define the most important groups of threats like: agricultural land use, construction industry, intensive forest activities, looting, mining and natural erosion (*fig. 10*). The evaluation of possible threats depends on the available data and on the subjective evaluation of the site location. In all countries agriculture and building activities seem to be the biggest threat to the Iron Age heritage. Important element except in Croatia seems to be looting of graves, due to the easy identification of tumuli in the field. In Slovenia and Austria the intensive forest activities often create damage on tumulus cemeteries, which are especially well preserved in forests. Natural erosion, also connected with deforestation, can create additional damage on archaeological sites.

Fig. 10: Possible threats for archaeological sites dated in the Early Iron Age.

The discussed threats to the archaeological heritage are closely connected to the current land use (*fig. 11*). In Austria, Hungary and Slovenia the Iron Age sites are evenly dispersed in agricultural, artificial and forested areas. More than one type of current land use can be present at one site. In Croatia the agricultural areas prevail. Depositions of artefacts or single finds in water bodies and wetlands are rather a rear phenomena in all countries, except Slovenia with great finds from the river Ljubljanica and Ljubljana Moor.

Fig. 11: Different land use on archaeological sites dated in the Early Iron Age.

Topic Promotion of archaeological heritage and its integration in tourism

For the evaluation of tourism potential of sites the methodology from a published study “Archaeological Biography of a Landscape on the Styrian-Slovenian Border”¹². For the integration of an archaeological site in tourism the most important elements are accessibility, visibility, infrastructure and surrounding offers. It is also connected with the securing of long term management, which was discussed already in the topic monument protection.

One of the most important issues in tourism is the accessibility of the tourist attraction (*fig. 12*). Elements, which were considered are: 1 – accessible by public transport, 2 – accessible for individual tourist groups and 3 – inaccessible. For our evaluation we used mostly general maps, since it was not

¹² Matija Črešnar, Marko Mele, Karl Peitler, Manca Vinazza (edit.) 2017, Archäologische Biographie einer Landschaft an der steirisch-slowenischen Grenze / Arheološka biografija krajine ob meji med avstrijsko Štajersko in Slovenijo. Schild von Steier, Beiheft 6/2015, Graz. <http://www.interarch-steiermark.eu/publikationen.html> (accessed 20.6.2019).

possible to visit all the sites. Sometimes it was not possible to give a clear answer just by using the maps. Generally in all countries the archaeological sites are accessible, but mostly in individual groups and by car. Between 20 and 30% are accessible also by public transport and also bigger groups with busses. The accessibility can be hindered by different issues, as for example deep in the forests or in national protection zones, restricted private property, military zone, mining area etc. The inaccessibility seems to be higher in Austria in comparison with other countries, but the main reason seem to be in the location of sites in remote areas, then the lack of public transport.

Fig. 12: Accessibility of archaeological sites dated in the Early Iron Age.

The visibility of the Iron Age heritage is generally better as for many other periods, since in many cases the tumuli and the earth ramparts of settlements were preserved over millennia (*fig. 13*). On the other side we have a lot of tumulus cemeteries, which have been flattened by agricultural activities and are only visible on aerial photos. Often even if the monuments are still preserved, they are visible only for the professionals, because they lack interpretation. Interpreted sites are well represented in Slovenia. In all countries the reconstructed and interpreted sites are reaching only 3-5% from all sites.

Fig. 13: Visibility of archaeological sites dated in the Early Iron Age.

For tourism visible, interpreted or reconstructed sites are a precondition, but also infrastructure (parking, toilets, food...) are needed. Complete infrastructure seems to be better at sites in Hungary and Slovenia, than in Austria and Croatia (*fig. 14*). The same seems to be for the basic infrastructure. More than a half of all sites in Austria, Croatia and Slovenia have no infrastructure at all.

Fig. 14: Tourist infrastructure in the vicinity of archaeological sites dated in the Early Iron Age.

Even if an archaeological site has a perfect infrastructure, visibility and accessibility the success of its integration in the touristic offer depend on general tourism development in the broad region around it (*fig. 15*). In Austria, Slovenia and Hungary the tourism in 22-38% of the regions with Iron Age sites seem to be good developed and is also intensively under development. Positive situation seems to be especially in Slovenia with only 8% of location with no tourism

attempts, while in Croatia the Iron Age sites are not located in the best tourism regions. In case of Croatia we have to consider, that the tourism regions at the Adriatic coast are not part of the evaluation.

Fig. 15: Touristic potential of the surrounding of archaeological sites dated in the Early Iron Age.

Recommendations for transnational strategies based on the data evaluation

The aim of our analysis of the data entered in the Iron-Age-Danube database is to filter trends in the topics archaeological research, monument protection and promotion and touristic use of Iron Age heritage in the four participating countries of the Danube region.

The data analysis on the research topic shows that archaeological excavations are still the major method used in archaeology (*fig. 3 and 4*). Non-invasive prospection methods are on the up-rise. The amount of specialized analysis like different methods for environmental reconstruction (e.g. environmental survey, geomorphological research...) remains relatively small (*fig. 4*). One of the important goals of the Iron-Age-Danube project is to shift the focus from single sites to whole landscapes and therefore fostering prospection methods, which can cover large areas in a short time, and environmental research should be a priority. Another important issue for archaeological research is also to combine different methods on single sites, in order to get optimum results from the given resources.¹³

¹³ Czajlik et al, 2019, 31-33.

Monument protection in the four countries has partly different traditions and approaches, different legislation and different resources. Therefore, a comparison is quite difficult. One important issue in securing successful monument protection is to take steps towards a stable long-term management, which should incorporate all three topics, monument protection, research and tourism. Three countries, besides Slovenia, need to make fast progress in securing the heritage status for the archaeological sites (*fig. 16*), since new research technologies in recent years produced much more data on archaeological heritage, than a few decades ago. The major threats in the monument protection of Iron Age sites seems to come from intensive land use in agriculture, forestry and building sector (*fig. 16*). Different approaches to different sectors need to be considered. Tumuli, most recognisable monuments of the Iron Age in the region, can be easily found in the woods, where they are still preserved. Therefore, in some countries looting of the archaeological monument still seems to be a major problem.

Fig. 16: Cultural heritage status and threats of archaeological sites dated in the Early Iron Age in all four countries.

On the topic of tourism and the possibilities for promotion of Iron Age heritage we discussed different standards of the sites in order to be developed to tourist points. Major issues are visibility, accessibility, infrastructure and surrounding. If we look at the joint tables for all four countries two issues need additional attention (*fig. 17*). On one side the visibility of archaeological heritage, which is generally a challenge in archaeology, and on the other the tourism infrastructure on the sites. For the visibility of sites we can use classic tools like boards, small exhibitions or new digital tools like augmented and virtual reality. A combination of them with very diverse narrations and other existing monuments to a single landscapes, often creates a successful, sustainable use of archaeological heritage for tourism.

Fig. 17: Accessibility, visibility, infrastructure and surrounding of archaeological sites dated in the Early Iron Age in all four countries.

Conclusion and outlook

The analysis of the data on Early Iron Age sites in Austria, Croatia, Hungary and Slovenia tried to find the differences and similarities in the research, protection and touristic use of this heritage in a part of the Danube region. The main goal of the database and the analysis was to extract some major issues, which are faced by this archaeological heritage, in order to create support for the creation of transnational strategies. Despite the different data sets from the countries and partly subjective decision making during the entering of the data, we could extract some trends for all three major topics, which should allow the project partnership to create a more pointed and applicable strategies.

After the analysis of the data in the database and the comparison of legislation and methods in the published methodological tool, the work will continue on wording of the strategies and afterwards the creation of national action plans, which should show the needed steps in each country for the implementation of strategies. We would like to thank the Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities (ACDH) of the Austrian Academy of Sciences for the development of the database and their support during the entering and analysing of data. We would also like to thank all colleagues working at partner institutions in researching and entering the data.

Literature

Zoltan Czajlik, Matija Črešnar, Michael Doneus, Martin Fera, Anja Hellmuth Kramberger and Marko Mele (edit.) 2019, Researching archaeological landscapes across borders. Strategies, Methods and Decisions for the 21st Century. Archaeolingua 2019.

Appendix 1 – Research methods terminology used in the Iron-Age-Danube database

Detailed research methods terminology used in the Iron-Age-Danube database in form of a thesaurus including short descriptions and translation to Croatian, German, Hungarian and Slovenian is available in an online Iron-Age-Danube thesaurus: https://vocabs.acdh.oeaw.ac.at/iad_thesaurus/en/

1 st order concept	2 nd order concept	3 rd order concept	4 th order concept		
remote sensing survey	satellite imaging	spaceborne photography			
		spaceborne imaging spectroscopy			
		spaceborne multispectral imaging			
		spaceborne laser scanning			
		spaceborne thermography			
		spaceborne radar imaging			
	airborne sensing	aerial photography		total coverage	
				observer directed	
		aerial thermography			
		airborne multispectral imaging			
		airborne imaging spectroscopy			
		airborne laser scanning			
		airborne radar imaging			
		airborne magnetometer survey			
		low altitude survey	UAV photography survey	kite aerial photography (KAP) survey	
				balloon aerial photography (BAP) survey	
	pole aerial photography (PAP) survey				
	terrestrial survey	geophysical survey	ground-penetrating radar survey		
magnetometry survey					
earth-resistance survey					
electromagnetic induction survey					
electrical resistivity tomography survey					
magnetic susceptibility survey					
metal detecting survey					
microgravity survey					
terrestrial seismic survey			seismic refraction survey		
			seismic reflection survey		

	field-walking survey	intensive field-walking survey	
		non-intensive field-walking survey	
		undetermined field-walking survey	
		shovel test	
	geomorphological survey	climate research	
		hydrological survey	
		lithology research	
		tectonics research	
		topography research	
	surface geometry survey	GNSS survey	
		image-based modelling	
		terrestrial laser scanning	
		total station survey	
underwater survey	acoustic ground discrimination radar		
	underwater seismic survey	3D seismic survey	
		bathymetric survey	
		multi beam echo sounder survey	
		side scan sonar survey	
		single beam echo sounder survey	
		sonar survey	
		sub bottom profiling survey	
	underwater photography		
environmental survey	archaeobotany	charcoal analysis	macroscopic charcoal screening
		palynology	phytolith analysis
			pollen analysis
		starch grain analysis	
	archaeoparasitology		
	archaeozoology		
	soil analysis	geochemical analysis	heavy mineral analysis
			phosphate analysis
		particle size analysis	
		soil micromorphology	
excavation	arbitrary level excavation		
	core drilling		
	flotation		
	microstratigraphic excavation		
	sieving	dry-sieving	
		wet-sieving	

	stratigraphic excavation			
	test pit			
	trial trench			
desktop assessment	historical landscape analysis			
	historical aerial photographs analysis			
	historical literature research			
artefact studies	stylistic studies			
	technological studies			
	usage studies			
anthropological studies				
supporting analysis	dating	amino acid recemization dating		
		archaeomagnetism		
		Carbon-14 dating		
		dendrochronology		
		electron spin resonance dating		
		fission track analysis		
		Fluorine, Uranium and Nitrogen tests		
		Lead isotope dating		
		luminescence dating	infra-red	stimulated
			luminescence	
			optically	stimulated
			luminescence	
			thermoluminescence	
			mitochondrial DNA	
		Oxygen isotope analysis		
		Potassium Argon dating		
		relative dating		
		Uranium series dating		
	elemental and molecular analysis	amino acid analysis		
		atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS)		
Auger-electron spectroscopy (AES)				
capillar electrophoresis				
electron probe microanalysis (EPMA)				
gas chromatography				
liquid chromatography				
nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR)				

	mass spectrometry	isotopic ratio mass spectrometry (IRMS)
		isotopic ratio mass spectrometry (IRMS)
		isotopic ratio mass spectrometry (IRMS)
		isotopic ratio mass spectrometry (IRMS)
		inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS)
	Fourier-transform Infrared spectrometry (FT-IR)	
	Raman spectroscopy	
	inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-AES)	
	molecular spectroscopy	
	neutron activation analysis (NAA)	
	optical emission spectrometry (OES)	
	proton induced X-rays (PIXE) and gamma rays (PIGME)	
	synchrotron-induced radiation	
	X-ray fluorescence	
	X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy	
crystallography	X-ray (powder) diffraction (XRD)	
microscopic examination	scanning electron microscopy (SEM)	
	transmission electron microscopy	
	polarised light microscopy	
metallographic analysis		
laser ablation		

Appendix 2 – Decision options on the topic of monument protection used in the Iron-Age-Danube database

Topic	1 st level decision option	2 nd level decision option
Current land use	agricultural areas	arable land
		permanent crops
		pastures
		heterogeneous agricultural areas
	artificial surfaces	urban fabric
		industrial, commercial and transport units
		mine, dump and construction sites
		artificial non-agricultural vegetated areas
		single building
	forests and semi-natural areas	forests
		shrub and/or herbaceous vegetation association
		open spaces with little or no vegetation
water bodies	inland waters	
	marine waters	
wetlands	inland wetlands	
	coastal wetlands	
Threats	agriculture/land use	
	construction/industry	
	intensive forest activities	
	looting	
	mine suspected area	
	natural erosion	
Topic	Decision options	
Cultural heritage status	yes	
	no	
	partially	
	in process	
Natural heritage status	yes	
	no	
	partially	
	in process	
Ownership	private	
	public	
	private/public	
	information not available	

Appendix 3 – Decision options on the topic of promotion and tourism used in the Iron-Age-Danube database

Topic	Decision options
Accessibility	1 – accessible by public transport
	2 – accessible for individual tourist groups
	3 – inaccessible
	4 - information not available
Visibility	1 – reconstructed and interpreted onsite
	2 – visible, but not interpreted
	3 - invisible archaeological heritage
	4 - information not available
Infrastructure	1 – complete infrastructure
	2 – basic infrastructure
	3 – no infrastructure
	4 - information not available
Long-term management	1 – long-term care ensured
	2 – short-term care ensured
	3 – no care foreseen or possible
	4 - information not available
Potential of surroundings	1 – touristic region with excellent infrastructure
	2 – touristic offer in development
	3 – no or little attempts for tourism
	4 - information not available